

UNVEILING KRISHNALEELA IN THE ART OF MANJIT BAWA

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Abstract. *Contemporary Indian artists have enriched the art world by blending sacred symbols and mythological themes with personal expression, creating a distinctive visual language that conveys profound messages and wisdom. Manjit Bawa, born in Dhuri, Punjab, in 1941, exemplifies this approach. His works vividly depict Krishna, influenced by Sufi philosophy and Indian scriptures. Using vibrant colors and symbolic imagery, Bawa's paintings explore themes of love and spirituality through Krishna's stories, prompting viewers to reflect on the deeper meanings of these ancient narratives. His art celebrates and reinterprets Krishna's mythological tales, offering both visual and intellectual engagement.*

Keywords: Myth and art, Manjit Bawa's work, Krishna tales.

1. Introduction

Numerous notable contemporary Indian artists have left a significant mark with their artworks, seamlessly blending the sacred symbolism of religious motifs and mythological narratives. Their distinct viewpoints give birth to a quasi-religious, cryptic language that communicates idealistic messages. Embedded within the mythological content, their inspirations carry a sense of wisdom. Raised in a society rich in religious heritage, artists were immersed in mythological tales from childhood. Consequently, their inspirations intertwine with their individual expressions, resulting in a multitude of artworks that present varied perspectives on Indian religions and mythology. These artists aimed not only to explore religious and mythological themes but also to convey messages of love among people and within their social spheres. Their impactful messages through art prompt society to reconsider its origins and values. (This paper is inspired by the literature found in the works of Ions¹ and Panda².)

2. The Artist

Manjit Bawa, a visionary artist, was born in '1941' in 'Dhuri', a small town in Punjab. He pursued his art education in Delhi and London. Bawa emerged during a time when Indian artists were blending traditional Indian culture with newfound freedom in Indian art. He is renowned for creating vibrant compositions infused with the spiritual essence inspired by Sufi philosophy. Drawing inspiration from Indian scriptures such as the Mahabharata, the Ramayana, and the Puranas, as well as Sufi poetry, Bawa's work resonates deeply with spiritual themes. Drawing from his engagement with myths and Sufi philosophy, Bawa has remarked, "I find a wealth of wisdom in the scriptures. Sufi philosophy has taught me that humanity and animals can coexist harmoniously." The artist's use of semi-religious symbols and mythological figures like Durga, Kali, Shiva, and Krishna stems from his childhood experiences. He explains, "In my world of imagination, these figures are very real. I learned about them through childhood stories and fables told by my father. As I grew older, I encountered them again in literature, music, poetry, and art." His depiction of deities and animals thus developed a unique visual language that enriched his storytelling and metaphors.

Animals play a crucial role in Manjit Bawa's paintings as well as in Indian mythology. He depicted animals that are closely tied to deities, such as the bull with Shiva, the cow with Krishna, the lion with the Goddess, and the elephant with Buddha, indicating their symbolic significance. In his artwork, elements are presented either as solitary figures or in groups against plain, single-colored backgrounds. Bawa created an interaction between the characters in his paintings and the viewers by using simplified figures with tonal gradations in colors like pink, red, blue, and purple. These figures are distinguished by their rounded contours, flowing lines, and diverse gestures. He illustrated famous legends and symbols, methodically setting them against vivid, flat-colored backgrounds.

2.1 The Classical Realm of Manjit Bawa

Analyzing Manjit Bawa's work through the lens of *rasa*—a concept that involves a heightened perception crucial to the appreciation of art, music, dance, theatre, and literature—can amplify the emotional impact of his paintings. This resonance may connect directly or indirectly with heroic, empathetic, marvelous, and

quiescent emotions among the nine enumerated rasas. Rasa is thought to transcend the ordinary, providing a hyperphysical and transcendental experience. Influenced by his training at the London School of Printing and his exposure to Pahari miniatures, Tantric frescos of Himalayan Buddhism, and the Kalighat patachitra style, Bawa incorporated various stylizations that formed a composite Indian metaphor, challenging the Western modernism of his time. His move away from academic realism and embrace of native influences marked a pivotal shift in his artistic journey. Through his art, Bawa sought to cultivate moral discernment among viewers, subtly bridging the gap between the worldly and the divine.

The violent riots of 1984 impacted the artist's life and art, yet he chose not to depict violence in his paintings. He stated, "I use both Hindu icons and Islamic icons in my work...but I don't want to harm anyone." Instead of aggression, he conveyed messages of love and peace through natural elements like fresh green paddy fields, gatherings of calm animals, and flute players in his paintings. Characters take on a mythical quality when portrayed as icons with their popular symbols or objects, depicted in action while performing their deeds, such as Krishna as a pastoral musician with flute and cows, Shiva with a bull, and a goddess on a tiger. The artist adopted the rasa theory from Indian mythology to express the intensity of expression and the intention behind each divine task performed for humanity's benefit. "Manjit is possibly the only artist who locates the humor of myths in his art without utmost seriousness."³

3. Krishna in Bawa's Art

Krishna, a highly venerated figure in Hindu mythology, has been portrayed by countless artists throughout history. His earthly life is held up as a paradigm for humanity, illustrating the importance of adhering to one's duties to transcend the struggles of life and foster love and compassion on earth. As Krishna, Vishnu made his eighth incarnation as 'Purnavatara,' a divine form that fully assumes human existence, embodying the essence of ideal divine love and serving as a protector of the natural world. This incarnation is celebrated for its embodiment of both spiritual and earthly virtues, symbolizing the harmony between the divine and the mundane.

In the artwork of Manjit Bawa, Krishna is depicted in various evocative roles that highlight his multifaceted nature. Bawa's portrayal often presents Krishna as a pastoral

lover, deeply connected with the rural and natural world, emphasizing his role as a nurturer and protector. Additionally, Krishna is frequently shown as a savior, underscoring his role in guiding and uplifting humanity. Most notably, Bawa represents Krishna as a flute player, a symbol of his divine music and its power to enchant and inspire, reinforcing the timeless and transcendent nature of Krishna's presence in both art and spirituality.

3.1 Krishna with flute

Krishna's flute represents both freedom and love, with its sound, known as 'Omkara,' thought to have emerged from the flute and played a role in the creation of the world. For devotees, the sound of Krishna's flute evokes spiritual bliss, dissolving ego and inspiring complete surrender to the Lord. In Manjit Bawa's paintings, Krishna is often portrayed as 'Murlidhara'⁴ or 'Venugopal,'⁵ depicted playing his flute in the forest. According to legend, the mesmerizing music of Krishna's flute enchanted not only the cowherd girls of Braj village but also the gods. In many of Bawa's paintings, Krishna is portrayed with his flute, distinguished by the blue hue of his body.

PLATE-1

Untitled (Bhavna)

20 x 14 inch.,

Reproduction on paper,

Year- 2000

Source: Marvel Art Gallery

In above painting (plate-1), Krishna is depicted wearing a crown of peacock feathers while playing the flute. Set against a plain red background, Krishna's upper body, from head to stomach (excluding the waist and legs), is painted blue with brown hair. He

faces the left side of the canvas, and the simplicity of his form makes him easily recognizable. A golden yellow garment resembling a scarf drape over Krishna's shoulder and extends down to a white cow beneath him, which appears calm and content, seemingly enchanted by the flute's music. Krishna's rounded arms hold the flute to his mouth, seamlessly blending with the rest of his body, including his rounded stomach. Although only Krishna's upper body is visible, an imaginary line suggests the lower portion of his form, linking him to the cow through the flowing scarf. The painting is dominated by warm red tones, yet the artist effectively conveys the soothing music of Krishna's flute. Through this portrayal of Krishna, Bawa also expresses his thoughtful and opinionated reflections.

PLATE-2

Untitled

20 x 14 inch.,
Reproduction on paper,
Year- 2000
Source: Tanya Baxter Art
Gallery

The revered figure is depicted in a different light, surrounded by wild dogs instead of cows, as seen in plate-2. In his artistic work, Krishna is depicted as both Krishna and Ranjha, representing a fated and idealistic hero. As a result, Bawa's portrayal of Krishna encompasses multiple dimensions, blending divine and human qualities, as well as mischievous and romantic elements. Manjit Bawa's first depiction of Krishna, titled *Purple Piper* in 1978, features rich yellows and purples⁶. This portrayal also reflects Krishna's well-known affection for animals, a theme that appears in several of Bawa's paintings.

3.2 Krishna Quells the forest fire

The artist illustrates a well-known episode from the Bhagavata Purana, where Lord Krishna saves animals from a forest fire. In this depiction, Krishna is shown in his iconic tribhanga pose, standing on one foot at the center of the canvas (Plate-3).

PLATE-3

Untitled

60 x 100 inch.,
Acrylic on Canvas,
Year- 2000
Source: Tanya Baxter
Art Gallery

Instead of the forest setting described in the original narration, Manjit Bawa chose a vivid red background. Krishna's beloved cows are grouped into three clusters, with a total of twenty-two cows portrayed in various actions—some running, others bending their necks towards the ground, and some gazing up at Krishna with their tongues out, expressing their love for their savior. Besides white, Bawa used additional tones such as blue, green, and yellow to depict the cows. Above, the canvas features orange flames moving rhythmically, which Krishna is depicted as drawing into his mouth as if handling them like a cloth. The scene conveys a sense of urgency but lacks any elements of horror or tension. Krishna, depicted in deep blue and wearing a yellow dhoti, performs his task with calm confidence and without apparent effort.

2.3 Krishna Lifting Govardhana Parvat

PLATE-4

Govardhana

60 x 100 inch.,
Oil on Canvas,
Year- 2000

Source: Tanya Baxter
Art Gallery

Another compelling depiction of Krishna's heroic acts in the royal setting of Vrindavana is portrayed by Manjit Bawa (plate-4). This painting revisits the story where Krishna lifted the Govardhana Hill to protect the people from torrential rain. The original tale highlights the conflict between two cults: one dedicated to Indra and the other to the cowherd god Krishna. In Bawa's painting, Krishna is set against an intensely bright red background, holding up a mountain shaped like an umbrella with the small finger of his left hand. He is dressed in a vibrant yellow garment that covers most of his body, leaving only his blue face and hands visible. Krishna's right hand reaches upwards, supporting a faint, mound-like shape. The painting also features men, women, children, and animals, all of whom are intently observing Krishna. The mountain, depicted in a small size and barely visible, seems to emerge from the background in a lighter tone. Only a few figures are shown under its shelter, symbolically representing the entire universe. Krishna is positioned slightly away from the other figures, who are arranged with slight gaps to create a sense of distance against the plain background. The figures, dressed primarily in white with touches of purple and green, look towards Krishna, while the animals are depicted in their usual manner. The background, devoid of dark clouds, heavy rain, or wind as described in the original story, emphasizes the prominence of the central figure.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, contemporary Indian artists have significantly influenced the art world by integrating religious symbolism and mythological narratives with their distinct perspectives. This blend creates a quasi-religious language that communicates idealistic messages and wisdom inherent in mythological content. Raised in a society steeped in religious heritage, these artists naturally merged their inspirations with personal expressions, resulting in diverse artworks that offer various interpretations of Indian religion and mythology. Their art delves into religious themes, emphasizing messages of love and harmony within society. Manjit Bawa, in particular, stands out for his vibrant compositions inspired by Sufi philosophy and Indian scriptures, prominently featuring Krishna. Bawa's work, characterized by simplified figures and tonal gradations, creates a unique visual language that intertwines the sacred with the everyday. His depictions of Krishna, whether as a pastoral lover, a savior, or a divine musician, prompt viewers to reflect on their values and origins. Through such art, these artists foster a deeper appreciation of cultural and spiritual heritage, encouraging unity and introspection.

Conflict of Interest: Author has no conflict of interest.

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